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Estimation of the environmental damage of floods in Russia at the end of the 20th century

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Abstract. This paper deals with outlining the main causes of floods. We analyze statistical data on the number of largest floods and the number of people in Russia affected by this phenomenon. We also classify floods by their causes and reveal the defining relationship between the number of floods and the number of spring high waters caused by melting snow and ice. This paper states the positive and negative aspects of using reservoirs as tools of changing nature for human benefit. We justify the need of combining engineering and non-engineering means of flood protection and evaluate the environmental damage of floods.

1. Introduction

Right now the issues of ensuring safe operation of hydrotechnical installations are becoming increasingly important.

According to [1], the number of emergencies on hydrotechnical installations on river basins in Russia and worldwide has significantly increased over the last 100 years. These emergencies caused large economic and environmental damage and also human casualties (figure. 1).

Figure 1. The tendency of the growing number of largest floods per year in Russia from 1902 to 2001.

Analysis of these emergencies enables us to formulate the main reasons causing them [2, 3]:

- Poor technical condition of hydrotechnical facilities
- Obsolescence of the systems for monitoring condition of hydrotechnical facilities
- Human factor
- Change of meteorological conditions.

The first two reasons can be eliminated to taking certain organizational measures requiring different capital and operational expenses. However, special attention should be paid to the human factor and the overall precipitation volume increase caused by the global change of meteorological conditions.

According to [4], some of the reservoirs of the Techa cascade of water bodies have shown stable water level growth. The level has grown by one meter between 1989 and 2001. The analysis of water balance components indicates that the main reason of reservoir water level growth is the change of meteorological conditions in the region in the last 10-20 years.

Figure 2. Mean annual and seasonal precipitation anomalies (mm/month), averaged for the territory of Russia, 1936-2016: b – trend slope (mm/month/10 years); D – trend contribution to the total variance (%).

The frequency and (or) intensity of the extreme weather phenomena may change due to global warming [5]. Figure 2 presents the time histories of the average annual and seasonal precipitation anomalies in Russia and worldwide (11 year moving average is displayed for all time histories and the linear regression trends with the 95% confidence interval are shown for the years 1976-2016).

Anomalies have been calculated as deviations from the mean value for the years 1961-1990.

The smoothed curve is obtained by an 11-year moving average. The linear trend is evaluated for the period 1976-2016; b – trend slope (mm/month/10 years), D – trend contribution to total variance (%). The chart analysis shows that the mean spring precipitation in the south of Russia in the year 2015 was 119% of the normal value, especially in the central and southern districts of the European part of Russia (the precipitation was 143% of the normal value in the Central federal district).

The human factor is playing an increasingly significant part in the natural water regime and composition change. These changes are often caused by wanting to get instant benefits. Here the human factor includes building reservoirs, channels, reclamation works, water diversion systems and so on. These interferences in the natural water exchange cycle can lead to significant increase of the wave propagation time. For instance, the wave propagation time from Rybinsk to Yaroslavl has increased tenfold because regulation of the Volga stream flow[6].

The main causes (figure 3) of floods in Russia are melting of ice and snow during spring – 51% and rainfall – 42% [7].

Figure 3. Causes of floods in Russia.

Several types of floods occur: high waters, floods, ice-jam and clogged drains cause floods; at the Far East even tsunamis take place sometimes.

The predicted climate warming and the inevitable growth of river valley development will undoubtedly lead more frequent and more destructive floods. Therefore developing effective measures of flood protection and prevention is an urgent issue that has to be addressed by the national governments and local authorities. One should not forget that emergency prevention can reduce the flood recovery expenses by a factor of 50-70.

A reservoir is defined as a mean of transforming the nature in the interests of humans and their economic activities. Positive changes for the environment and the economic activity from using reservoirs include:

- Reduction or full elimination of such negative natural phenomena as floods, water shortages;
- Concentration and accumulation of water resources;
- Redistribution of streamflow between years and seasons of different dryness, between days and hours, creation of water areas, improvement of conditions for water transport;
- Hydrological regime transformation for the purpose of regular land irrigation, improved usage of bottomlands below dams and bottomland protection from overly frequent and lengthy floods;
- Involving the otherwise unproductive land in economic use by accumulating water resources on that and creating a water environment that can be productive in some cases (fish farming and fishing)
- Improvement of water supply for the population, especially in dry years and periods;
- Improving environmental conditions of the adjacent territories: water amenities, softening of climate.

The powerful upward trend of flood damage in all countries, including Russia, is primarily caused by economic development intensification of flood-prone territories. The experience of many years of all countries shows that engineering measures do not provide total safety from floods, as they are not capable of preventing the main causes of flood damage growth. It is necessary to develop and approve a unified flood protection concept including both the engineering and non-engineering measures. The latter should be aimed at stimulating the landowners to organize their activity in the flood-prone areas in such a way that the damage would be at a minimum in case of a flood.

2. Evaluation of environmental damage caused by river flooding

The river Eshkanon is the right affluent of the river Podkumok. It originates in mountains, it is a typical mountain river with rapid flow and steep slopes. It is classified by the water regime as a North Caucasus type river. It is characterized by intensive summer high waters and a stable winter low water. Frequent rainfalls and downpours significantly increase the number of floods. In this case the number of floods per year can exceed tens of times. Mountain rivers carry a very large amount of sediments. The river is carrying not just small soil particles but even stones and sometimes large stone blocks. The destructive force of the mountain flow is very large. During a flood it can not only deform the stream bed but even form the new one by moving from one side of the valley to the other. The slopes and speeds are reduced downstream and the river deposits the larger sediments and carries downstream only the smaller fractions [8, 9].

Mudflows are present on mountain rivers. The mudflows are occasional mud rock flows having large destructive force. The process of mudflow forming has to do with lengthy accumulation of the rock weathering products in the upstream mountain river water. The products are carried by the river affluents to their mouths and deposited there in the form of “evacuation cones”.

During floods caused by strong downpours the rapid river flow carries these cones along with bank devastation products. Temporary jams can be formed at narrow points or at river turns. When they are broken a wave full of sediments, mud, stones, rocks, washed away trees and other debris is formed. All this mass goes crashing downstream by destroying all the obstacles in its way.

The Eshkanon river water regime is determined by the long spring-summer flood and heavy rains. The main flow takes place in the spring-summer season. It is formed by solid and liquid precipitations and also by melting high-mountain snows in the upper part of the river basin.

The water quality study was conducted along the whole reservoir length and also across it. To that end water samples were collected and analyzed at the water sections shown in figure 4.

The low water period turbidity was 10 mg/L, while during the flood it was reaching the maximum value of mg/L (figure 5). Therefore during low turbidity period lasting from 7 to 9 months the water is purified only by direct filtering in the water supply system.

Figures 4. Cross-sections for collecting and analyzing water samples:I–VII – reservoir cross-sections; 1–16 – numbers of samples in cross-sections.

Figure 5. Reservoir water turbidity for the years of observation.

3. Qualitative flood impact analysis

Waterlogging is the rise of groundwater level and the increase of soil moisture on built-up areas and on areas being built up. Waterlogging is caused by water balance change (water inflow is greater than outflow) due to the influence of the aggregate man-made factors at certain environmental conditions. It complicates construction and exploitation of a built-up territory and leads to environmental deterioration [10, 11, 12].

According to data provided by the State Committee of the Russian Federation on environmental protection right now waterlogging is the most widespread hazardous process. Its consequences can be dangerous or catastrophic.

The waterlogging process is mostly determined by the environmental conditions of the territories being built up: lithological composition, topography, soil filtration properties, groundwater infiltration recharge character.

Territory terrain determines the flow condition of rain and meltwater, therefore it strongly influences the groundwater infiltration recharge levels. Having no system of surface flow regulation, weak terrain roughness, presence of depressions, different kinds of cavities and lows create favorable conditions for groundwater accumulation [13].

Most of the studies point out that the main cause of waterlogging is losses of water due to poor operation and dilapidation of the water networks (gravity and pressure pipelines, sewage system, storm runoffs systems) reaching 15-38%.

The latest studies have shown that the surface waters contain a large mass of toxic organic and non-organic chemicals (table 1), as well as pathogenic microorganisms having a detrimental effect on the water body flora and fauna.

The problem of polluted surface flow monitoring on urbanized territories is being studied by many researchers [14, 15].

Quantitative and qualitative composition of rain and thaw water can only be predicted with a certain degree of probability. It is governed by a whole range of factors: geographic location, precipitation intensity and duration at different seasons, character of flow basin, sanitation condition, the predominant wind direction, proximity to industrial zones, presence of highways and transport loads [16, 17]. The concentration of adulterants in rainfall runoff is largely determined on precipitation intensity, dry weather period duration, and the previous rain [18]. This can be explained by the fact that the rainfall runoff is polluted due atmospheric air substance sorption, dilution and washing away

contaminants of the water collection basin and the rain runoff network [19]. The concentration of adulterants changes significantly; as a rule it rapidly reaches maximum and diminished by the end of a rain. The content of suspended solids, oil products and organics expressed in BOD units significantly changes as the rainfall runoff approaches the outlet cross-section.

Table 1.Composition of rainfall runoff.

Indicator Value. mg/L	Volgogram	Moscow	Astrakhan	Voronezh	Penza	Maximum concentration limit
pH	7.41-7.8	7-8	8.6-9.4	7.8-8.0	7.0-8.0	6.5-8.5
Lead	–	–	–	–	–	0.03
Copper	0.022	–	–	–	0.001-0.016	1.0
Zinc	0.039	–	–	–	0.02-0.12	1.0
Nickel	0.009				0.02-0.05	0.1
Suspended solids	113-5049	65-245	215-281	39-90	50-1544	20.0
Solidresidue	445.5-5718	1088-1935		200-266		1000
COD	75-239.1	15.3-21.6	57.6-195.0	60.2-120		30
BOD ₅	39.2-71.9				5.2-316	6
Oil products	0.75-3.0	12-17.5	95-197	45-52	0.125-47.5	0.3
Sulfates	126.8-215.8		195-212	48-55	63.4-792.0	500
Chlorides	98.1-149.4	51-190	323-451	91-111	36.9-86.7	350
Phosphates					0.06-5.44	3.5
Ammonia nitrogen	0.45-1.85				3.8-11.2	2
Nitrates	0.85-3				4.9-25.5	45
Nitrites	0.014-0.173				0-0.78	3.3

The experiments established that the concentration of suspended solids in the rainfall runoff close to rainwater sumps can be very volatile ranging from tens of milliliters per liter to 20000 milliliters per liter. The oil products content ranges from 0.25-2 mg/L to 80-100 mg/L [20]. The analysis shows that the suspended solids content is mainly influenced by rain intensity and the duration of the preceding dry period. The level of rainfall runoff pollution by oil products is greatly influenced by traffic intensity.

4. Main results and conclusions

It is necessary to combine non-engineering and engineering flood protection methods (flow regulation using reservoirs, building wall dams of near-river territories, straightening and deepening the river beds in order to accelerate flood water flow, building channels for channeling water waters in the natural terrain cavities, terrain level elevation). The former methods include developing economic and legal rules that take into account the specifics of using flood-prone territories. These norms include: restriction or full prohibition of the economic activities that can worsen the floods (deforestation, etc.), and also escalation of measures aimed at creating flow reduction conditions (autumn ploughing, switching to subsoil tillage, etc.). Besides one should choose such kind of economic activity that will

suffer the least severe damage from a flood. Making and publishing maps of flood-prone territories, besides their direct application, will help significantly in rapid flood damage evaluation including estimates of ground flooding levels. These estimates do not exist for most floods.

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